

Project Plan

[Name of the Writer]

[Name of the Institution]

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Introduction

Inventory management technology is a mix of hardware and software intended to add dependability to inventory bookkeeping, diminish episodes of burglary and encourage inventory reviews. Individual inventory things or groups of things could be furnished with RFID tags that recognize the thing sort, expense, value, shipment number, date of shipment and basically whatever other valuable data. Software inventory management arrangements supplant pen-and-paper frameworks, diminishing the time needed to record for inventory augmentations and subtractions.

Equipment

Laptop or Desktop Computer- Laptop or computer with wireless access can allow to her to manage her sales and create or manage inventory items.

Wireless Router – The wireless router will assure wireless access point for the laptop or computer. This modifies laptop to be mobile for inventory goals.

Barcode scanner – A barcode scanner is an electronic device for reading printed barcodes. This barcode scanner will be used with the mobile laptop for sales and inventory.

Barcode label printer – A barcode label printer is computer hardware for printing barcode labels or tags that will be attached to the inventory.

Printers/ Faxes – This equipments can be used for make an order, send faxes, print receipts, reports or etc.

Budgeting

Laptop or desktop computer

We can buy a Toshiba Satellite C855-S5343 PSCBLU 15.6 inch laptop with an i3-3110M processor, 2.4 GHz speed, 6GB DDR3 RAM, 500 GB 5400 rpm Hard Drive and Windows 8 Professional 64-bit operating system at a cost of \$459.99 (2013, Amazon).

Wireless router

We can buy media link wireless N broadband router for 49.99 (2013 Amazon) The media link provides fast speed and reliable variety. It will connect computers, wireless printers, and other Wi-Fi devices at speeds up to 150 Mbps. Internal antenna technology provides broad wireless coverage throughout your home. 150 Mbs- 2.4 Ghz- 802.11n w (2013, Amazon).

USB Barcode Scanner

We can buy newest model Tao Tronics TT-BS007 wireless cordless handheld barcode scanner bar code reader for 179.99 (Amazon 2013) Increases application design flexibility to better meet your specific needs. Cordless and anti-interference scanning with secure wireless transmission of data helps users increase productivity and cut costs while providing free movement throughout the workspace. It has an integrated non-volatile memory which secures data even when it is out of signal or powered off.

Barcode Label printer

We can buy a DYMO label writer 450 turbo high speed for 63.09 (Amazon 2013). If you want to get cheaper one, you can get around 15\$ too. DYMO Label version 8 software enables you to create and print address, shipping, file, folder and barcode labels.

Printer

We can buy a Brother HL 2270 DW compact Laser Printer with wireless Networking and Duplex. We can use it for many purpose such as printing receipts or reports, also we can use it as a fax machine.

Maintenance

Maintenance shouldn't be delayed for any reason. It is very important because these kinds of electronic devices can be broke easily. They can break for many reasons such as high heat: if they work nonstop more than 5 hours, they can get overheated, which the equipment cannot handle. Probably not in the first week but most certainly you can expect failure within three weeks. In that case you have to purchase new equipment which is not good for the business. Equipment takes four or more hours or more than 10% of its monthly maintenance budget to repair. If equipment fails three or more times per month, repairs need to be performed externally.

Software

Inflows Inventory oversees items and inventory. It keeps items sorted out with pictures, costs, and classifications. Inflow can undoubtedly handle 10,000+ items on a normal PC. It utilizes barcode scanners to deal with your inventory all the more rapidly and precisely. Inflow is perfect with most barcode scanners you can connect to your computer. It

tracks inventory in different areas uses sub-areas to all the more unequivocally track path numbers, canister numbers, and so forth. It gives a full history of any inventory developments or changes in accordance with track down any issues or robbery. It utilizes a basic work-stream to take requests and deduct inventory with a single click. It uses progressed work-stream to track more point by point things like transportation data, particular picking, and client returns. It functions admirably with professionally composed receipts. We can alter the logo, color and textual styles to suit your business' style. We can utilize the "Reorder Stock button" to consequently create buy requests for items that are low in stock.

Cost

We can have everybody working off the same data in real time utilizing multi-user mode. We can confine who has admittance to see or adjust utilization. Inflow permits you to make distinctive login users, each with an alternate set of access rights, for example, who can reorder stock, who can make a deal or who can do inventory. Inflow permits you to rename any names or messages inside the product. Inflow coordinates with Excel or Quickbooks by importing and trading data in the business standard CSV group.

Inflow is offered in three different editions. They are available in basic, regular and premium. I recommend a purchase of regular edition for a cost of \$299. This will allow unlimited product listing and up to five user license. It also give you access to one of the essential reports which can give data on high demand items (inflowinventory.com). The total cost to completely set up this process will be approximately \$ 1350.